

Vanadium. Part XVIII. Oxo-vanadium(IV) Mixed Chelates with Tridentate Dibasic Hydrazone Schiff Bases and Bidentate Dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline)

R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan

Manuscript received 23 December 1972; revised 4 June 1973; accepted 18 July 1973

Oxovanadium(IV) mixed chelates having one tridentate dibasic hydrazone Schiff base anion and another neutral strong-field ligand. $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline) have been prepared. Their magnetic moments are normal. Infrared evidences reveal a six coordinate stereochemistry for vanadium. The complexes exhibit solvent dependent spectra.

As an extension of our interest on Schiff base complexes^{1,2} we now report some oxovanadium(IV) mixed chelates with one tridentate dibasic hydrazone Schiff base (Fig. 1; A $\rightleftharpoons$ B) and a neutral strong field ligand like α, α' -dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline).

A

B

The hydrazone Schiff bases employed are the products of interaction of a hydroxyaldehyde or a β -diketone with benzoyl hydrazide or salicylhydrazide.

Experimental

Benzoylhydrazide and salicylhydrazide were prepared according to standard procedures^{3,4}. Other reagents were of analar grade.

Preparation of the mixed chelates: Ethanol solution of the hydroxyaldehyde or β -diketone (0.01 mole) was refluxed with an ethanol solution of benzoylhydrazide or salicylhydrazide (0.01 mole) on a steam bath for 30 min. The filtrate from the treatment of syrupy vanadyl chloride (0.01 mole) and sodium acetate (0.02 mole) in ethanol was added to the Schiff base solution. After refluxing for 30 min. $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline) (0.01 mole) was added and refluxing continued for 1 hr. In most cases shining brown or orange crystals separated out from the solution. In other cases some solvent was removed and the solution cooled in a refrigerator

overnight. In a few instances water was added to initiate precipitation. Drying was done over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The chelates are usually soluble in chloroform and pyridine but less so in ethanol, benzene and ether. Characterization data appear in Table 1.

Methods of analyses, magnetic and spectral measurements have previously been described^{1,2}.

Results and Discussions

The mixed chelates conform to the composition $[\text{VO}(\text{AA})(\text{SB})]$ (AA = $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline and SBH_2 = tridentate dibasic Schiff base). These are usually coloured brown and are quite stable to air. Their paramagnetic moments indicate a +4 oxidation state for vanadium. Besides, characteristic vanadyl stretch and d-d ligand field bands are present in all the mixed chelates. The magnetic moment values also indicate the absence of any interaction between neighbouring vanadium ions. The chelates are non-electrolytes in dimethylformamide which rules out any ionic formulation.

The assignments of the main infrared bands are shown in Table 2. These assignments were based on an appreciation of the relevant bands of the complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{o-phen})\text{SO}_4]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{dipy})\text{SO}_4]$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}(\text{dipy})]^{5,6}$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{o-phen})_2]^{6,7}$ as also of the free

TABLE 1. CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) MIXED CHELATES

Mixed chelate	Colour	% Vanadium		% Nitrogen		μ_{eff}	(B.M.) (°K)
		Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)		
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salbenzoyl)]	Red	10.12	10.51	11.50	11.52	1.63	312
[VO(dipy)(Salbenzoyl)]	Brown	10.88	11.06	11.88	12.14	1.83	312
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Hynapbenzoyl)]	Red	9.74	9.53	10.14	10.46	1.79	312
[VO(dipy)(Hynapbenzoyl)]	Black brown	9.74	9.98	10.58	10.95	1.72	312
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Salsalicoyl)]	Brown	9.97	10.15	10.80	11.15	1.67	300
[VO(dipy)(Salsalicoyl)] $\cdot$ 1.5H ₂ O	Orange	10.24	10.09	11.20	11.08	1.62	311
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Hynapsalicoyl)]	Brown	9.20	9.23	9.95	10.14	1.83	307
[VO(dipy)(Hynapsalicoyl)]	Brown	9.63	9.64	10.33	10.60	1.82	296
[VO(dipy)(acacbenzoyl)]	Brown	11.31	11.61	12.47	12.75	1.64	311
[VO(dipy)(acacsalicoyl)]	Orange	11.11	11.18	11.99	12.27	1.71	307
[VO(dipy)(Resoreylsalicoyl)] $\cdot$ 0.5H ₂ O	Orange red	9.99	10.13	11.07	11.13	1.63	308

Abbreviations : Salbenzoyl H₂ = salicylaldehyde benzoyl hydrazide Schiff base; Salsalicoyl H₂ = salicylaldehyde salicyl hydrazide Schiff base; Hynapbenzoyl H₂ = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde benzoylhydrazide Schiff base; Hynapsalicoyl H₂ = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde salicylhydrazide Schiff base; acacbenzoyl H₂ = acetyl-acetone benzoyl hydrazide Schiff base; acacsalicoyl H₂ = acetylacetone salicylhydrazide Schiff base; Resoreyl salicyl H₂ = Resoreylaldehyde salicyl hydrazide Schiff base; *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline; dipy = $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl.

TABLE 2. ASSIGNMENT OF THE MAIN INFRARED BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE OXOVANADIUM(IV) MIXED CHELATES

Schiff base/Mixed Chelate	V = O	C = N	C = O	Dipy/ <i>o</i> -phen
Salbenzoyl H ₂	-	1613 m	1667 s	-
Hynapsalicoyl H ₂	-	1610 vs	1650 s	-
[VO(dipy)SO ₄]	971 m	-	-	769 s 1316 s 1439 vs 1600 s
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)SO ₄]	980 m	-	-	645 m 855 m 877 m 1627 s
[VO(dipy)(salbenzoyl)]	952 vs	-	-	763 s 1308 m 1439 s 1600 s
[VO(dipy)(acacbenzoyl)]	962 vs	1600 m	-	769 s 1308 m 1439 s 1600 vs
[VO(dipy)(acacsalicoyl)]	962 vs	1600 vs	-	769 s 1308 m 1439 s 1600 vs
[VO(dipy)(resoreylsalicoyl)]	980 s	1600 vs	-	763 vs 1326 m 1439 s 1600 vs
[VO(<i>o</i> -phen)(Hynapsalicoyl)]	962 vs	1600 s	-	645 m 847 s 870 m 1600 s 1613 vs

Schiff bases. A vanadyl stretch at 966 ± 14 cm⁻¹ suggests a monomeric VO unit⁷. Coordinated imine group bands overlap with dipyriddy/*o*-phenanthroline bands at ~ 1600 -1630 cm⁻¹. That the Schiff bases are coordinated in the imidol form (Fig. 1,B), is shown by the absence of the C = O stretch of the Schiff bases (Fig. 1,A) in the complexes. The infrared spectra suggest a six coordinate geometry for vanadium in these complexes.

The electronic spectra of the mixed chelates in the solid state and in non-donor solvents, such as chloroform, are alike. This behaviour indicates that the same chromophore exists in the two states. The absorption bands, however, are rather broad and are not well resolved. In donor solvents such as pyridine, as many as four bands appear in the visible region (Fig. 2). It may be noted that contrary to this behaviour, the oxovanadium(IV) mixed chelates containing dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) and tridentate dibasic salicyledene amino acid type Schiff bases exhibited similar spectra in solid state, in non-donor solvents and donor solvents². In view of the remarkable influence of pyridine in bringing about radical changes in the spectra two alternative explanations may be offered : (1) the tridentate Schiff base anion may function as a bidentate making one coordination site available to an incoming pyridine, (2) large excess of pyridine used as a solvent may knock off the dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline). Our experiments, however, will not distinguish between these alternatives.

If we disregard, for the sake of approximation, the chelate rings and consider only the immediate donor atom environment, of oxovanadium(IV) these mixed chelates may be treated on the C_{2v} symmetry and the Ballhausen-Gray model⁸ extended to these systems. On this model $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ transition of the present chelates shows splitting into two components in pyridine. This splitting is ~ 3 -4 kK. In pyridine a sharp band appears around 16-16.6 kK, which

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of [VO(dipy)(salbenzoyl)] in different media
 ----- (A) Mull spectra
 - - - - - (B) Complex (0.005m) in Chloroform
 _____ (C) Complex (0.005m) in Pyridine
 Optical density for (A) is arbitrary.

TABLE 3. ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) MIXED CHELATES

Mixed chelate	State	Absorption		Bands (kK) ϵ_{molar}		
			Band III	Band II	Band I	
[VO(dipy)(Salbenzoyl)]	Mull	23.25; 22.2			13.7 ; 12.5	
	Chloroform				13.7 (38) 12.3 (36)	
	Pyridine	18.18 (175)		16.66 (133)	15.38(63) 11.23(27)	
[VO(o-phen)(Salsalicoyl)]	Mull	23.5 ; 21.7			13.88; 12.05	
	Chloroform				13.7 (35) 11.97(30)	
	Pyridine			16.13 (78)	13.88(32) 11.76(35)	
[VO(dipy)(Salsalicoyl)]1.5H ₂ O	Mull	23.5			14.7 sh	
	Chloroform				14.49(44) b	
	Pyridine	18.5(217)	17.24(178)	16.00(90)	12.19(37) sh	
	Mull	23.25			11.23(30) b	
[VO(dipy)(Acacbenzoyl)]					13.88 b	
	Chloroform				12.82 sh; b	
	Pyridine				13.88(58) b 15.62(85) sh 11.90(33) b	
[VO(dipy)(Acacsalicoyl)]	Mull	23.51			13.88 b	
	Chloroform				13.79(47) b	
	Pyridine	18.35(143)	17.24(154)	16.13(144)	14.70(80) sh 12.50(20) b	
[VO(dipy)(Resorcylsahicoyl)]	Mull	23.51; 22.2			13.88 b	
	Pyridine	18.69(360)	17.39(349)	16.13(179)	11.49(28)	

sh = shoulder; b = broad.

is assigned as $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition. Besides these bands there appears a band around 17-18 kK which is assigned as $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$. Another band around 18.6 kK in some of the complexes may have charge transfer origin. The absorption bands around 23 kK are intraligand transitions as shown by very high absorption similar to those of the free Schiff bases. The electronic spectra of the mixed chelates appear in Table 3. Fig. 2 represents [VO(dipy)(salbenzoyl)]. Multiband spectra have been reported for vanadyl N₁N' ethylene bis (5-chlorosalicylaldehydeimine). Bands at 21.7, 17.5, 15.15 and 12.75 kK have been assigned as d-d ligand field bands and one at 24.4 kK as a charge transfer band⁹. The molecule has been considered to have a C₂ symmetry.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 33.
2. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 919.
3. L. GATTERMAN and H. WIELAND, *Laboratory Methods of Organic Chemistry*, McMillan, London, 1960, p. 153.
4. M. S. KACHHAWAHA and A. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 361.
5. P. C. H. MITCHELL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 963.
6. P. A. MARZILLI and D. A. BUCKINGHAM, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 2259.
7. C. G. BARRACLOUGH, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
8. C. G. BALLHAUSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
9. I. Y. KASPAROVA and V. V. ZELENTOV, *Sh. Strukt. Khim.*, 1968, **9**, 532.